

ALTERNATING CURRENT ELECTROLYSIS. PART VI. ELECTROLYSIS OF SULPHURIC ACID SOLUTIONS WITH GOLD ELECTRODES

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Effect of passing symmetrical alternating current in sulphuric acid solutions with gold electrodes, has been investigated. As observed previously, the current efficiency appears to decrease with frequency of alternation, concentration of electrolyte and progress of electrolysis. Higher current density favours the formation of electrode gas. Hydrogen peroxide is formed during electrolysis.

A theory has been advanced to explain the observed effects, based on recombination reactions taking place between the products liberated during consecutive half-cycles. Alternate oxidation and reduction of the electrode surface has been found to take place.

The results of experiments carried out with gold electrodes in sulphuric acid solutions in alternating current electrolysis are presented in this paper. The effects of frequency, current density, duration of electrolysis and concentration of electrolyte have been studied to elucidate the electrode reactions during A.C. electrolysis.

Marsh (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1920, 97A, 124) investigated the chemical effects of passing an A.C. of 40 cycles per second frequency between gold electrodes in dilute sulphuric acid, and found the rate of gas evolution to fall off with time and to increase with current density. He obtained definite evidence for the formation of an oxide during electrolysis. He suggested that alternate oxidation and reduction of the electrode surface might be taking place during A.C. electrolysis. Marsh, however, did not analyse the electrode gases obtained at the two electrodes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental arrangement was the same as that used in previous investigations (this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 278). The electrodes were made from bullion gold and measured 1 × 2 cm. These were fused into J-shaped glass tubing. The electrode gases were collected in gas collecting cups attached to gas burettes. The composition of electrode gas was determined by absorption in alkaline pyrogallol. The electrodes were cleaned with hot concentrated nitric acid and heated in a spirit lamp flame. These were then washed with water and rubbed with filter paper and immediately used. This procedure was found to furnish reproducible results.

During electrolysis it was observed that as soon as the current was switched on, provided that the current density was sufficiently high, gas evolution started at both the electrodes, but the rate of gas evolution fell off with time. The electrode at the end of the experiment was found to have been covered with a loosely adhering, orange-coloured deposit, insoluble in acids. Tests showed the deposit to be of elementary gold.

Effect of Frequency.—Table I records the effect of frequency on the current efficiency of gas evolution as well as on the composition of gas evolved at each electrode.

TABLE I

Electrolyte: $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Ampere hours passed = 0.4.

Frequency per sec.	Electrode I.			Electrode II.			% Current efficiency of gas evolution.
	Total gas.	H ₂ .	O ₂ .	Total gas.	H ₂ .	O ₂ .	
Current = 600 ma.							
10	72.6 c.c.	50.4 c.c.	22.2 c.c.	68.8 c.c.	47.0 c.c.	21.8 c.c.	58.7
20	22.4	16.2	6.2	23.1	15.7	7.4	18.0
30	12.5	8.3	4.2	10.8	7.6	3.2	9.7
40	7.2	4.8	2.4	6.8	4.6	2.2	5.8
50	6.0	4.0	2.0	5.4	3.8	1.6	4.7
Current = 200 ma.							
5	56.6	38.1	18.5	52.4	35.2	17.2	49.40
10	21.5	14.4	7.1	18.0	13.0	5.0	16.40
20	6.2	4.2	2.0	5.8	4.0	1.8	4.98
30	2.0	1.4	0.6	1.8	1.2	0.6	1.60
40	1.2	...	...	1.2	...	...	0.99
50	1.0	...	...	1.0	...	...	0.83

It can be seen from the data presented above that the current efficiency decreases with frequency of alternation. This has been a general observation in the case of A.C. electrolysis. If current efficiency were plotted against frequency of alternation, the curve would have the same shape as that obtained in earlier investigations. However, the results obtained in the present investigation on being compared with those obtained with platinum electrodes under identical conditions (Joshi, *loc. cit.*) show that the current efficiency with gold electrodes is greater. It will also be seen that the volume or composition of the gas evolved at the two electrodes is never the same.

Effect of Current Density.—Table II shows the effect of current density (C.D.) on the volume and composition of gas evolved.

TABLE II

Electrolyte: $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

C.D. (ma/cm ²).	Duration of exp.	Electrode I.			Electrode II.			% Current effi- ciency of gas evolution.
		Total gas.	H ₂ .	O ₂ .	Total gas.	H ₂ .	O ₂ .	
Frequency = 20 per second.								
50	120 mins.	6.2 c.c.	4.2 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	5.8 c.c.	4.0 c.c.	1.8 c.c.	4.98
100	60	27.8	19.3	8.5	18.8	15.0	5.8	19.4
150	40	22.4	16.2	6.2	23.1	15.7	7.4	18.9
200	20	43.4	30.0	13.4	34.0	23.6	10.4	46.4
250	20	44.5	30.7	13.8	47.8	32.6	15.2	44.2
Frequency = 40 per second.								
50	120	1.2	...	...	1.2	...	...	0.99
100	60	6.0	4.1	1.9	2.8	1.9	0.9	3.65
200	30	22.2	16.0	6.2	17.8	12.6	5.8	16.70
300	20	31.5	21.9	9.6	39.0	26.6	12.4	29.40

It will thus be seen that higher C.D. favours the formation of hydrogen and oxygen at the electrode. When the current efficiency is plotted against the current density, a linear curve at higher values of current density is obtained.

Effect of Electrolyte Concentration.—Table III records the effect of concentration of electrolyte on current efficiency.

TABLE III

Frequency = 10 per sec. Current = 600 ma. Time = 40 mins.

Electrolyte conc.	E l e c t r o d e I.			E l e c t r o d e II.			% Efficiency.
	Total gas.	H ₂ .	O ₂ .	Total gas.	H ₂ .	O ₂ .	
N/20	86.8 c.c.	60.0 c.c.	26.8 c.c.	81.3 c.c.	55.7 c.c.	25.6 c.c.	69.6 c.c.
N/10	72.6	50.4	22.2	68.8	47.0	21.8	58.7
N/5	24.7	17.0	6.8	21.2	14.7	6.5	19.1
N	10.6	7.4	3.2	9.8	6.8	3.0	8.5
2N	4.8	3.2	1.6	4.2	2.8	1.4	3.7

Effect of Time.—It was observed that with time the rate of gas evolution fell off. Table I shows the effect of time on the volume of gas collected at an electrode.

TABLE IV

Electrolyte: N/10-H₂SO₄. Current = 200 ma. Frequency = 20 per sec.

Electrode I.		Electrode II.	
Time.	Volume.	Time.	Volume.
3 mins.	1.1 c.c.	4 mins.	1.2 c.c.
6	1.95	7	2.2
10	2.8	11	3.0
14	3.6	16	3.8
20	4.6	21	4.8
28	5.8	29	5.8
42	7.3	43	7.4
60	9.2	60	8.6

It will thus be seen from the typical data presented above that the current efficiency of gas evolution decreases with the concentration of electrolyte as well as with the progress of electrolysis.

Formation of H₂O₂.—Qualitative tests indicate the presence of hydrogen peroxide in the electrolyte after a run of electrolysis as also the absence of persulphate in the electrolyte. Experiments were performed to find out a correlation between the amount of H₂O₂ formed and the composition of the electrode gas.

TABLE V

Electrolyte: $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$.

Frequency per sec.	Current.	Total H_2 .	Total O_2 .	H_2O_2 (g. $\times 10^{-3}$).	Available O_2 from H_2O_2 .	Total O_2 liberated (sum of columns 4 and 6).	$\frac{1}{2}$ Volume of H_2 evolved.
Ampere hours passed = 0.2							
5	400 ma	62.8 c.c.	25.5 c.c.	9.400	3.10 c.c.	29.40 c.c.	31.40 c.c.
20	600	15.9	6.8	3.096	1.02	7.82	7.95
10	500	50.0	24.2	2.185	0.72	24.92	25.00
10	300	27.5	13.7	0.015	0.05	13.75	13.75
10	200	13.9	5.8	3.035	1.00	6.80	6.95
Ampere hours passed = 0.4.							
40	600	13.9	5.7	3.49	1.15	6.85	6.95
40	1000	34.0	15.2	4.86	1.60	16.80	17.00
30	400	7.2	3.0	1.71	0.60	3.60	3.60

It will be seen from the above table that if the total available oxygen from hydrogen peroxide formed in the electrolyte is added to the total oxygen evolved at both the electrodes, the total volume, thus computed, is equal to half the volume of hydrogen evolved. The agreement is within the experimental error though, where the volumes of gas collected are large, the difference between columns 7 and 8 (above) is quite considerable.

DISCUSSION

The primary reactions which should take place in respect of consecutive anodic and cathodic discharge at a gold electrode are :

Consecutive anodic and cathodic discharge at the same electrode leads to recombination of discharged products. Thus :

The fact that current efficiency is low in A.C. electrolysis shows that a large proportion of discharge products is removed by the process of reversal during the opposite half-wave. Definite evidence has been obtained by the author, with respect to the formation and reduction of Au_2O_3 (to be communicated later). As frequency is increased, the duration of a half-cycle becomes smaller so that the products discharged at the

electrode have less chance to evolve as gas; on the other hand, other processes, viz. reversal and ionisation of adsorbed gas, may predominate, leading to a lowering in current efficiency with frequency.

Higher current density will result in a greater amount of products being discharged in a unit time, leading to a greater concentration on the electrode surface. If the frequency of alternation is not very large, the discharged atoms during the half-cycle will combine and evolve as gas at a more rapid rate than at a lower current density. Moreover, a greater concentration during the cathodic cycle of hydrogen atoms will bring about a faster reduction of auric oxide formed during the previous half-cycle. Thus, the discharge of H^+ ions and the combination of hydrogen atoms discharged on the electrode will be facilitated. Also, during the anodic cycle, the rate of formation of the oxide and the evolution of oxygen will increase with current density. However, oscillographic work on the system, $Au-H_2SO_4-Au$, has shown that the area of electrode covered with the oxide does not increase linearly with current density. There seems to occur a saturation of the surface in respect of oxide formation, oxygen evolution taking place on the surface left bare. It is therefore easy to visualise that at a high current density, the coulombs contained in the half-cycle will not all be used for the formation of the oxide; on the contrary, the coulombs available for the liberation of oxygen will be larger at a higher current density.

The formation of hydrogen peroxide probably takes place according to the same mechanism as that proposed in the case of platinum electrodes (Part III, *loc. cit.*). Thus:

The conditions are favourable for the above reactions since consecutive half-cycles will leave H and O_2 on the surface of the electrode.

The lowering of current efficiency with progress of electrolysis can be explained on the basis of the picture presented above. With continued electrolysis, due to alternate oxidation and reduction of the electrode surface, the surface area of the electrode continually increases, thus lowering the effective current density. Thus the rate of gas evolution will decrease with the progress of electrolysis.